

Reconstruction of Velocity Fields from MRI Data

Using Pyramidal Lucas–Kanade Sparse Optical Flow
for Abdominal Aortic Aneurysm Assessment

Hanae SOULAMI

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Abstract

This study investigates the reconstruction of two-dimensional velocity fields from cardiac cine-MRI sequences in the context of Abdominal Aortic Aneurysm (AAA) assessment. We implement and evaluate the *Pyramidal Lucas–Kanade* (PLK) sparse optical flow algorithm on both short-axis and long-axis MRI sequences of an AAA patient. Feature detection relies on the Shi–Tomasi corner criterion; multi-resolution Gaussian image pyramids handle large inter-frame displacements. A systematic sensitivity analysis of the search window parameter (`winSize`) demonstrates that values in the range $[(10, 10)–(15, 15)]$ produce the most physiologically consistent velocity profiles, with average linear velocities of 8.6–14.7 mm/s and a characteristic systolic peak at $T=0.44$ s (short-axis) and $T\approx 0.20$ s (long-axis). Algorithm accuracy is validated against ground-truth synthetic data: minimum tracking error $\approx 2.79\%$ at `winSize` = (11, 11). Angular velocity analysis confirms an anti-clockwise vortical flow pattern ($\omega \approx +0.13$ to $+0.22$ rad/s) in the ascending aorta, consistent with published helical aortic hemodynamics.

1. Introduction

1.1 Clinical Context: Abdominal Aortic Aneurysm

The aorta is the principal conduit of the systemic circulation. An **Abdominal Aortic Aneurysm (AAA)** is defined as a full-thickness dilatation of the abdominal aortic diameter exceeding 1.5 times its normal caliber (≥ 1.5 cm), most commonly involving the infrarenal segment. AAA carries a substantial risk of rupture, associated with mortality rates exceeding 80% if untreated [5].

Epidemiologically, risk rises markedly after age 50, with higher prevalence in men. Pooled rupture risks are 3.5% for diameters [5.5, 6.0] cm, 4.1% for [6.1, 7.0] cm, and 6.3% for AAA ≥ 7 cm [6]. Women with AAA of [5.0, 5.9] cm face up to four times the rupture risk of men, motivating earlier intervention thresholds (5 cm) in female patients.

1.2 Motivation

Velocity field reconstruction from medical imaging provides essential hemodynamic information for AAA risk stratification. Phase-Contrast MRI (PC-MRI) is the gold standard but requires specialised acquisition protocols. Standard cine-MRI sequences — routinely acquired — offer untapped potential for motion estimation

via computer vision techniques without additional acquisition cost.

1.3 Objectives

- Implement and validate PLK optical flow on synthetic data with known ground truth.
- Reconstruct linear and angular velocity fields from short- and long-axis cine-MRI sequences.
- Conduct a systematic `winSize` sensitivity analysis.
- Characterise the physiological relevance of recovered hemodynamic patterns.

2. Theoretical Background

2.1 Optical Flow Constraint Equation

Let $I(x, y, t)$ denote pixel intensity at position (x, y) at time t . Under brightness constancy and spatial coherence, Taylor-series expansion yields the *Optical Flow Constraint Equation* (OFCE):

$$I_x V_x + I_y V_y = -I_t \quad (1)$$

where I_x, I_y, I_t are partial image derivatives, and $\mathbf{V} = (V_x, V_y)^T$ is the unknown flow vector. Since (1) is under-determined (one equation, two unknowns), additional constraints are required.

2.2 Lucas–Kanade Least-Squares Solution

The LK method [1] assumes constant flow within a local $m \times m$ neighbourhood Ω centred on the pixel of interest. This yields an over-determined system $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{b}$ solved by least squares:

$$\mathbf{v} = \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} \sum I_x^2 & \sum I_x I_y \\ \sum I_x I_y & \sum I_y^2 \end{pmatrix}^{-1}}_{\mathbf{M}^{-1}} \begin{pmatrix} -\sum I_x I_t \\ -\sum I_y I_t \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

The 2×2 structure tensor $\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A}$ must be well-conditioned (large eigenvalues λ_1, λ_2) for reliable estimation — the basis of the **Shi–Tomasi** detector:

$$R = \min(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) > R_{\text{thresh}} \quad (3)$$

2.3 Pyramidal Extension

The basic LK method assumes small inter-frame displacements. The *Pyramidal LK* (PLK) framework [2] builds a Gaussian image pyramid of L_m levels and processes coarse-to-fine: flow computed at level L_m is propagated as an initial guess to level $L_m - 1$, then refined iteratively down to full-resolution $L = 0$. This enables reliable estimation of displacements up to $\text{winSize} \times 2^{L_m}$ pixels. Practical values are $L_m \in \{2, 3, 4\}$; for 640×480 images $L_m = 4$ yields sub-images of 320×240 , 160×120 , 80×60 , 40×30 .

2.4 Angular Velocity

Given a reference centre $O = (x_0, y_0)$ of the aortic lumen, the angular velocity ω of a tracked point is:

$$\omega = \frac{\Delta\theta}{\Delta t} = \frac{\arctan\left(\frac{\Delta y_f}{\Delta x_f}\right) - \arctan\left(\frac{\Delta y_i}{\Delta x_i}\right)}{\Delta t} \quad (4)$$

This quantity relates to linear velocity by $V = R\omega$, where R is the distance from the point to O .

3. Methodology

3.1 MRI Data Description

Two cine-MRI sequences of an AAA patient (Rigshospitalet, January 2020) were analysed, each comprising 25 frames over one cardiac cycle:

- **Short-axis view:** transverse 2D cross-section for in-plane flow quantification and wall motion estimation (Fig. 1).
- **Long-axis view:** longitudinal 2D section for axial flow characterisation.

Acquisition parameters: TR = 7.0 ms, slice thickness 1.50 mm, flip angle 1.41° , 25 frames per cardiac cycle.

Figure 1: Short-axis 2D cine-MRI frame of the AAA. The aortic lumen appears as the central circular structure.

3.2 Feature Initialisation and Update Strategy

A binary mask of the aortic lumen was manually segmented. Two initialisation modes were used:

- **Line mode:** 10 equidistant points along a vertical or horizontal axis crossing the lumen.
- **Full-lumen mode:** all mask pixels, for sensitivity analysis.

A key contribution is the **periodic reset (update) strategy:** after each frame transition tracked points are re-anchored to their initial positions, preventing drift accumulation and artificial voids in the velocity field.

3.3 Algorithm Configuration

Table 1: Fixed PLK algorithm parameters.

Parameter	Value
maxLevel (pyramid depth)	4
Iterations per pyramid level	3
Convergence threshold ε	0.03
winSize range tested	(4, 4) to (30, 30)
Optimal winSize (synthetic)	(11, 11), error $\approx 2.79\%$

3.4 Velocity Computation

For each tracked point p_i at frame f , the PLK displacement vector $\mathbf{d}_i = (dx, dy)$ is converted to physical velocity:

$$|\mathbf{V}_{\text{lin}}| = \frac{\sqrt{dx^2 + dy^2} \times s_{px}}{\Delta t} \quad [\text{mm/s}] \quad (5)$$

where s_{px} is the pixel spacing (from DICOM metadata) and $\Delta t = T_{RR}/25 \approx 0.04$ s.

4. Results

4.1 Algorithm Validation on Synthetic Data

A 10-frame synthetic video of a moving red disk with known ground-truth positions was used for quantitative validation. Table 2 compares PLK estimates at two window sizes against ground-truth velocity magnitudes.

Table 2: Synthetic validation: ground-truth velocity (px/frame) vs. PLK estimates and per-frame error (%).

Fr.	V_{GT}	$V_{(4,4)}$	$V_{(15,15)}$	Err. (%)
2	440	437.8	437.3	0.50 / 0.62
3	510	516.9	497.8	1.33 / 2.46
4	400	359.1	399.0	11.39 / 0.24
5	380	341.5	379.7	11.27 / 0.08
6	300	287.0	318.6	4.51 / 5.84
7	300	250.5	278.1	19.78 / 7.88
8	300	285.8	317.7	4.96 / 5.56
9	540	518.8	527.5	4.09 / 2.38
10	650	755.4	647.8	13.95 / 0.34
Mean error				7.98 / 2.82

`winSize= (15,15)` substantially outperforms the small window (mean error 2.82% vs. 7.98%). Figure 2 shows the complete error curves as a function of `winSize` and number of iterations.

Figure 2: (Top) Average tracking error (%) vs. `winSize`, minimum at (11, 11), error $\approx 2.79\%$. (Bottom) Error vs. iterations, convergence after 3 iterations.

4.2 Velocity Fields: Short-Axis View

4.2.1 Directional Velocity Fields (Line Tracking)

Tracking 10 points along vertical and horizontal lines through the aortic lumen reveals a characteristic *anti-clockwise circular flow* across all 25 frames (Figs. 3–4). Points near the wall display low tangential velocities; the central stream shows high-velocity vectors consistent with laminar core flow.

Figure 4: Velocity fields of a horizontal line, short-axis view (frames 1–22). Anti-clockwise circular flow is confirmed in both orientations.

4.2.2 Full-Lumen Dense Velocity Field

Extending tracking to all lumen pixels provides a dense velocity field. The vector map confirms the anti-

clockwise vortical flow across all 25 frames; the periodic reset prevents void formation (Fig. 5).

Figure 5: Dense velocity field for all aortic lumen pixels, short-axis view (frames 1–22). The anti-clockwise vortical flow of the ascending aorta is visible.

4.2.3 Sensitivity Analysis: Linear Velocity vs. winSize

Average linear velocity decreases monotonically with increasing winSize in both conditions (Fig. 6). Table 3 summarises the results.

Figure 6: Average linear velocity (mm/s) vs. winSize, short-axis view. Blue = with periodic reset; Orange = without reset.

Table 3: Short-axis linear velocity by winSize. †Without periodic reset.

winSize	V_{\min}	V_{\max}	\bar{V}	V_{\min}^{\dagger}	V_{\max}^{\dagger}	\bar{V}^{\dagger}
	(mm/s)					
(4, 4)	24.2	57.1	40.8	36.3	84.2	54.4
(10, 10)	8.8	25.4	14.7	9.4	32.2	15.8
(12, 12)	6.5	22.1	11.4	7.1	26.5	12.3
(15, 15)	5.0	15.9	8.6	5.3	16.1	8.4
(20, 20)	3.4	8.9	5.9	3.4	10.3	6.3
(30, 30)	1.8	6.2	3.3	1.7	5.9	3.4

4.2.4 Temporal Linear Velocity Curves — Short-Axis

Figure 7 shows the velocity-time curves over the 25-frame cardiac cycle for six winSize values. A consistent **systolic peak at $T = 0.44$ s** is observed for winSize $\in \{(10, 10), (12, 12), (15, 15)\}$, confirming physiological coherence in this optimal range.

Figure 7: Average linear velocity (mm/s) over time for six winSize values of short-axis view. Consistent systolic peak at $T=0.44$ s is visible for winSize $\in \{(10, 10), (12, 12), (15, 15)\}$.

4.2.5 Angular Velocity: winSize Sensitivity and Temporal Curves

Angular velocity analysis (reference centre $O = (186, 133)$ px) confirms the rotational nature of the flow. With the update strategy, mean ω is positive (anti-

clockwise) for all intermediate `winSize` values; without reset, a systematic clockwise drift is observed (Table 4, Figs. 8–9).

Figure 8: Average angular velocity (rad/s) vs. `winSize`, short-axis view. Positive = anti-clockwise.

Figure 9: Angular velocity (rad/s) over time for six `winSize` values of short-axis view. Blue (with reset) is anti-clockwise dominant; orange (without reset) shows systematic drift.

Table 4: Angular velocity by `winSize` of short-axis view. †Without periodic reset.

<code>winSize</code>	ω_{\min}	ω_{\max}	$\bar{\omega}$	ω_{\min}^{\dagger}	ω_{\max}^{\dagger}	$\bar{\omega}^{\dagger}$
(4, 4)	-2.08	2.41	-0.08	-2.25	2.78	-0.45
(10, 10)	-0.78	1.43	+0.22	-1.67	0.87	-0.61
(12, 12)	-0.54	1.52	+0.19	-1.37	1.00	-0.64
(15, 15)	-0.84	0.89	+0.13	-1.32	0.01	-0.74
(20, 20)	-0.53	0.49	+0.09	-1.33	-0.13	-0.87
(30, 30)	-0.28	0.36	+0.03	-1.45	0.02	-0.95

4.3 Velocity Fields: Long-Axis View

The long-axis reconstruction captures pulsatile axial flow along the aneurysmal segment (Fig. 10).

Figure 10: Long-axis 2D cine-MRI frame of the AAA with tracked lumen points (colour-coded dots).

Table 5: Long-axis linear velocity ranges by winSize. †Without periodic reset.

winSize	V_{\min}	V_{\max}	V_{\min}^{\dagger}	V_{\max}^{\dagger}
	(mm/s)			
(4, 4)	19.4	86.5	27.7	86.4
(10, 10)	5.8	32.5	6.0	33.0
(12, 12)	4.6	28.9	4.8	29.0
(15, 15)	3.5	23.0	3.8	21.9
(20, 20)	2.1	17.3	2.3	17.4
(30, 30)	1.0	10.1	1.0	9.8

4.3.2 Temporal Velocity Curves with Systolic/Diastolic Identification

The long-axis temporal curves unambiguously reveal the cardiac cycle phases. For intermediate winSize values, a clear **systolic peak** is identified at $T \approx 0.20-0.25$ s, followed by the systole–diastole transition and diastolic decay (Figs. 12–13). Peak velocities of 23–33 mm/s are consistent with published aortic wall velocities in AAA patients.

Figure 11: Dense velocity field reconstruction of long-axis view, frame 2. Each coloured point is an individually tracked lumen pixel.

4.3.1 Linear Velocity vs. winSize of Long-Axis

The same monotonic decrease as in the short-axis view is observed (Table 5).

Figure 34: Linear velocity over time for winSize = (4,4)

Figure 35: Linear velocity over time for winSize = (10,10)

Figure 36: Linear velocity over time for winSize = (12,12)

Figure 37: Linear velocity over time for winSize = (15,15)

Figure 12: Linear velocity (mm/s) over time for winSize (4, 4), (10, 10), (12, 12), (15, 15) of long-axis view. Red annotations mark systolic peak, systole, and diastole.

Figure 38: Linear velocity over time for $\text{winSize} = (20,20)$

Figure 39: Linear velocity over time for $\text{winSize} = (30,30)$

Figure 13: Linear velocity (mm/s) over time for $\text{winSize} (20,20)$ and $(30,30)$ of long-axis view. The systolic peak persists but with reduced magnitude due to spatial over-smoothing.

5. Discussion

5.1 Optimal winSize and Algorithmic Trade-offs

The sensitivity analysis consistently identifies $\text{winSize} \in \{(10,10), (12,12)\}$ as the optimal range across both MRI views. Small windows (< 8) generate spurious large displacements as points escape the search region; large windows (> 20) over-smooth the motion field, suppressing systolic peaks and reducing velocity dynamic range. The sweet spot balances spatial precision with robustness to noise and inter-frame motion magnitude.

Convergence in 3 iterations (error plateau at $\approx 2.79\%$) is notable for computational efficiency. The update strategy is critical: without periodic reset, angular velocity exhibits a systematic clockwise drift incompatible with known aortic flow physics.

5.2 Physiological Interpretation

The anti-clockwise vortical pattern in the short-axis ascending aorta is consistent with helical aortic flow driven by left ventricular rotational momentum [7]. The systolic peak at $T = 0.44$ s (short-axis) and $T \approx 0.20$ s (long-axis) reflects the timing of peak aortic outflow following ventricular ejection. Velocity magnitudes of 8–15 mm/s (average) and 23–33 mm/s (systolic peak, long-axis) are clinically plausible for the aortic wall in an AAA context.

5.3 Limitations and Future Work

- **Single patient** — multi-centre validation is required.
- **2D analysis only** — through-plane components need 4D flow MRI [7].
- **Manual segmentation** — deep-learning automation would improve scalability and reproducibility.
- **No PC-MRI comparison** — quantitative validation against phase-contrast measurements within the same subjects is planned.

Future extensions should investigate dense optical flow (Farnebäck), deep learning-based methods (RAFT, FlowNet), and integration with finite-element biome-

chanical models for patient-specific rupture risk prediction.

6. Conclusion

This study demonstrates the feasibility of reconstructing hemodynamic velocity fields from standard cine-MRI sequences using the Pyramidal Lucas–Kanade algorithm. Key contributions are:

- Minimum tracking error $\approx 2.79\%$ at $\text{winSize} = (11,11)$, converging in 3 iterations.
- Optimal range $\text{winSize} \in \{(10,10), (12,12)\}$ for aortic cine-MRI.
- Clear systolic peak identification: $T = 0.44$ s (short-axis), $T \approx 0.20$ s (long-axis).
- Anti-clockwise vortical flow confirmed ($\omega \approx +0.13$ to $+0.22$ rad/s).
- Periodic reset strategy essential for physiologically consistent angular estimates and full lumen coverage.

The proposed framework is a cost-effective, non-invasive hemodynamic assessment tool extractable from routinely acquired cine-MRI sequences, with direct potential for clinical AAA surveillance and patient-specific rupture risk stratification.

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